

SCIENCE EUROPE

2020 ANNUAL REPORT

BUILDING SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE IN EUROPE & BEYOND

**SCIENCE
EUROPE**
Shaping the future of research

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2020 IN REVIEW

THE TRANSFORMATION NO ONE SAW COMING

“Scientific research became more relevant and important than ever in 2020.”

**NO ONE COULD HAVE
PREDICTED THE WAY
IN WHICH OUR WORLD WOULD
TRANSFORM WITH THE ARRIVAL
OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC.**

Science Europe, which brings together the expertise of the largest and best-known research organisations in Europe and a commitment to jointly push the frontiers of how scientific research is produced and delivers benefits to society, became more relevant and important than ever in 2020.

Despite the challenges and turbulence of the past year, Science Europe continues to thrive. Building on the collaborative nature of its work, Science Europe excelled at supporting the work of its Member Organisations by issuing aligned recommendations on a variety of key research policy topics, as this report illustrates. The association also continued to make a significant contribution to the EU's future work by providing concrete recommendations to the European Commission and consistently supporting the European Parliament in its advocacy for a stronger budget for Horizon Europe and for hallmark programmes such as the ERC and Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions. We very closely followed key files such as the preparations for the launch of Horizon Europe and the finalisation of the Multi-annual Financial Framework (2021–2027).

The year brought new energy for Science Europe, supported by a new Governing Board who took office in November 2019. Much effort has been dedicated to driving the strategic development of the association as we began developing the future Science Europe Vision and Strategy. After excellent dialogue with its Member Organisations, we look forward to a new phase of development for Science Europe.

I am honoured to lead the association alongside my fellow Governing Board members, supported by the Secretary General and the Science Europe Office in Brussels, and I congratulate them on another successful year. I would also like to thank Science Europe's many partners for their collaboration over the course of the last 12 months, including OECD, EUA, GRC, CESAER, DORA, and cOAlition S. Without our collaboration with the wider research community and many stakeholder groups, our outputs would not have been as effective. Finally, I would like to express my gratitude to Science Europe's Member Organisations whose commitment, trust, expertise, and engagement make our activities possible.

MARC SCHILTZ

PRESIDENT OF SCIENCE EUROPE

SECRETARY GENERAL OF THE NATIONAL RESEARCH FUND
OF LUXEMBOURG (FNR)

SCIENCE EUROPE 2020 - OUTPUTS AT A GLANCE

JANUARY

Science Europe shares the experiences of its Member Organisations in its publication and event on '**Implementing Research Data Management Policies across Europe.**'

Science Europe's **annual reception** welcomes friends and partners to mark the past year's achievements and highlight upcoming priorities.

A **dedicated event on GDPR** helps Member Organisations with information and legal advice to continue their international collaborations in a GDPR-compliant way.

MARCH

The Science Europe Office swiftly moves to remote work and adapts its operations as COVID-19 lockdowns take hold in Belgium and across the world.

In light of the COVID-19 situation, Science Europe requests the EC to adopt **special measures in Horizon 2020** calls and projects that provide flexibility on deadlines and conditions to comply with project proposals and reporting.

MAY

Science Europe calls on the EC to take into account the importance of the research sector as a producer and user of data in its **response to the Consultation on the European Strategy for Data.**

FEBRUARY

Science Europe releases the report of its **flagship study on Research Assessment Practices** and launches a consultation of its Member Organisations on research assessment processes.

The Science Europe Working Group on Open Access to Research Publications starts its **new mandate** and begins its study on the issue of **monitoring Open Access.**

APRIL

Science Europe sets up and co-ordinates **repositories of COVID-19-related activities** as launched by its Member Organisations and launches surveys to identify special measures and expected impact of the pandemic for funders and performers.

Science Europe organises a **workshop to develop recommendations on research assessment processes.** Alongside researchers, high-level representatives from the European Research Council, the Marie Curie Alumni Association, the Global Young Academy, and the European University Association participate.

JUNE

Science Europe calls on EU leaders to dedicate **increased funding for R&I** to meet the EU's ambitious objectives for a sustainable, healthy planet, and to ensure the global competitiveness of its research sector.

Science Europe meets the European Commission to present its recommendations on European Partnerships.

JULY

Science Europe calls on research organisations to **continuously evaluate their research assessment processes** to ensure that they are effective, efficient, fair, and transparent in its new **'Position Statement and Recommendations on Research Assessment Processes.'**

Following the deal reached by the European Council on 21 July, Science Europe calls for a **higher budget for Horizon Europe.**

SEPTEMBER

Science Europe's President, Secretary General, and Governing Board members speak and moderate numerous sessions at **ESOF 2020, the pan-European conference dedicated to R&I.**

Science Europe outlines numerous topics that should be further addressed to create **the best possible start for Horizon Europe** in response to the EC Consultation on its First Strategic Plan 2021-2024.

Science Europe publishes its first thoughts on the **new European Research Area** - an ambitious plan calls for inclusiveness and collaboration.

NOVEMBER

Heads of national research organisations, Ministers and Secretaries of State for research, and European Commissioner Mariya Gabriel discuss post-COVID-19 recovery and resilience at **Science Europe's High Level Workshop on ERA.**

Science Europe launches a campaign to promote **the innovative research assessment practices of its Member Organisations.**

The EOSC Sustainability Working Group, co-chaired by Science Europe and EMBL, publish **'Solutions for a sustainable EOSC: A FAIR Lady report.'**

AUGUST

Science Europe and the OECD Global Science Forum team up and publish a report to identify ways to **optimise the operation and use of research infrastructures** at national level.

OCTOBER

Science Europe welcomes the adoption of the Bonn Declaration on **'Freedom of Scientific Research'** at the Ministerial Conference on European Research Area. The freedom of scientific research is a key principle of the success and sustainability of European research.

Science Europe signs the EU Manifesto for COVID-19 Research to **ensure that EU-funded coronavirus research results are made available in Open Access.**

Science Europe and the task group on Monitoring Open Access organise a workshop to discuss ways to monitor the status of research publications and progress toward OA.

DECEMBER

Twelve Science Europe members, with support of the Science Europe Office, launch **Weave**, a cross-European initiative to fund and support excellent international research projects.

Science Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC) organise the first in a series of events to promote **scientific exchange between European and Chinese researchers working on COVID-19-related topics.**

Science Europe and twelve Science Europe members join the newly launched **EOSC Association** as members and observer members.

MAP OF SCIENCE EUROPE MEMBERS

01 HRB			
05 Danmarks Grundforskningsfond Danish National Research Foundation			
09 DFG Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft			
13 HR^B Health Research Board			
17 LZP			
21 The Research Council of Norway			
25 ufiscdi			
29 CSIC CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS			
33 FNSNF FONDS NATIONAL SUISSE SCHWEIZERISCHER NATIONALFONDS FONDO NAZIONALE SVIZZERO SWISS NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION			
37 RESEARCH PERFORMING ORGANISATION</p>			

COVID-19

THE YEAR 2020 SAW A GLOBAL PANDEMIC ATTEST TO THE VALUE OF SCIENCE.

In the race for COVID-19 treatments and vaccines, Science Europe's Member Organisations (MOs) were at the forefront of the global response.

Dialogue with the European Institutions

As the pandemic peaked in Europe at the beginning of the year, Science Europe reached out to the EU institutions with important messages on behalf of its members. On 25 March, a letter was sent to the European Commission's Director-General for Research and Innovation (R&I) asking for flexible measures for research organisations and researchers to facilitate research activity under the exceptional circumstances. On 15 June, Science Europe issued a [position statement](#) calling for more investment in fundamental research, as well as a strategic and co-ordinated approach to long-term research to address the pandemic and its consequences. Science Europe also supported the First 'ERAvsCorona' Action Plan to leverage the research capacities of EU Member States and Associated Countries. On 13 October, Science Europe signed the EC's [Manifesto for EU COVID-19 Research](#), laying out principles for EU-funded COVID-19 research to make the results, publications, and data generated publicly available and accessible.

Supporting its MOs on pandemic-related issues was a top priority for Science Europe.

Activities of Science Europe and its Member Organisations

Online Overview of COVID-19 related activities

Supporting its MOs on pandemic-related issues was a top priority for Science Europe. An early survey allowed Science Europe to identify COVID-19 special calls and measures and understand the challenges faced by its MOs. These provided the basis to inform both international and European policy developments.

Science Europe's material was used in discussions with the Global Research Council (GRC) – see [page 26](#) - and the Global Research Collaboration for Infectious Disease Preparedness (GloPID-R).

As early as April, new MO calls for research proposals and MOs' special activities already demonstrated the immediate engagement of the scientific community in tackling the pandemics ([COVID-19 priority page](#)).

Scientists' Networking Workshops on COVID-19 – Collaboration with China

Collaboration between Science Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC) was developed following a proposal from the NSFC to organise networking events for scientists. On 14 December, a joint event on [COVID-19 prevention](#) gathered around one hundred researchers from across Europe and China. A follow up workshop (held in March 2021) focused on [COVID-19 social consequences](#).

EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA

THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA (ERA) IS AT THE HEART OF EUROPE'S AMBITION FOR A WORLD-LEADING AND SEAMLESS RESEARCH HUB.

It is meant as a space of research excellence with aligned research and innovation policies. Researchers, scientific knowledge, and innovation should circulate freely within the ERA. For the ERA to deliver on its promise, the EU must work closely with national R&I organisations as well as with pan-European research stakeholders, such as Science Europe.

EC's New Communication on ERA

Throughout 2020, Science Europe monitored the preparation of the [EC Communication on a new ERA for research and innovation](#) (September 2020), and of the [Council Conclusions on the new ERA](#) (December 2020). During this time, Science Europe engaged in discussions with EU Institutions. On the day the EC published its Communication, Science Europe issued [a reaction](#) welcoming the EC's high ambitions for the ERA and its commitment to leading the transition to sustainable and resilient societies.

Science Europe 2020 High Level Workshop on ERA

Twenty years after the ERA was created under the then-Portuguese Presidency of the Council of the EU, all eyes were cast on Portugal as it stood next in line for the 2021 EU Presidency. Science Europe's Portuguese member, the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) hosted the 12th edition of the High Level Workshop on ERA, together with the Portuguese Ministry for Science, Technology, and Higher Education (MCTES) and Science Europe. The event brought together high-level representatives from across the Science Europe membership, the EC, research ministries, and experts in research policy.

Researchers, scientific knowledge, and innovation should circulate freely within the European Research Area.

The High Level Workshop addressed the challenges for research mobility and career development in the ERA in the COVID-19 context and ways to develop a resilient ERA. Another important issue was how the research community should break away from the 'silo mindset', both in terms of cross-border collaboration and Open Science. The evolution and trends in research culture were discussed, as well as the need to reward a wider range of research contributions than the typical publications and datasets. A panel discussion with the European Commissioner for R&I Mariya Gabriel and research Ministers and State Secretaries focused on key areas for action in the coming years and on common policy action proposals. A clear intention of collaboration towards more aligned policies emerged. As was the case with previous editions of its annual High Level Workshop, Science Europe will take the event's outcomes into account to work with its members to reinforce the ERA.

FOR MORE DETAILS:

Please read the [Report on the High-Level Workshop 2020 on ERA](#) and check out the [High-Level Workshop Addresses](#).

EU FRAMEWORK PROGRAMMES

VIRTUALLY NOT A MONTH GOES BY IN THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH COMMUNITY WITHOUT DEBATE ON HORIZON EUROPE,

THE NEW FLAGSHIP EU FUNDING INSTRUMENT FOR R&I (2021–2027), OR ITS PREDECESSOR HORIZON 2020 (2014–2020).

Many Science Europe MOs make a major contribution to the research effort under the Horizon programmes. Others regularly collaborate with European Institutions on issues of leading research. Science Europe is therefore regularly consulted and heard by EU Institutions on the scope, functioning, and funding of these programmes.

EU Multiannual Financial Framework (2021–2027) and Horizon Europe Budget

2020 was marked by recurring political deadlocks over the EU's Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) for 2021–2027 and the Next Generation EU (2021–2024) recovery plan. Science Europe consistently advocated a stronger R&I budget. Two strategic statements, on [Horizon Europe](#) and on the [COVID-19](#) pandemic, were

Many Science Europe MOs make a major contribution to the research effort under the Horizon programmes.

published ahead of the European Council meeting on 19 June, urging Member States to allocate at least €135bn (€120bn in constant prices 2018) to Horizon Europe and invest more in fundamental science. A campaign was also organised over the summer supporting the European Parliament's efforts towards a larger Horizon Europe budget. A last-minute budgetary agreement was eventually brokered, resulting in a slight increase for Horizon Europe to reach €95bn. Whilst welcoming the deal, Science Europe nevertheless warned against the potential negative consequences of insufficient funding and foreseen delays in launching the first calls for proposals.

Monitoring the development of Horizon Europe

In 2020, Science Europe renewed [advocacy efforts](#) for Horizon Europe's timely implementation, highlighting important [cross-cutting issues](#) for the first Horizon Europe Strategic Plan (2021–2024), such as adequate R&I balance, a strong Open Science policy, and the role of social sciences and humanities. Science Europe also advocated a continued close collaboration with Associated Countries, at the forefront of which Norway, Iceland, Switzerland, and the UK. The monitoring, advocacy, and dialogue with the European Institutions was implemented in close co-operation with the Working Group on Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. Meetings to further the association's recommendations were organised with Science Europe's Presidency and top-level EC officials to discuss Horizon Europe, including Commissioner Gabriel (an early meeting in December 2019), and DG RTD Director-General Jean-Eric Paquet (March 2020).

European Partnerships

In parallel, Science Europe issued a paper underlining the main conditions for its members to efficiently take part in the new European Partnerships. A combination of events and strategic advocacy initiatives resulted in high-level meetings between MOs and EC's DG RTD officials. That strategy was defined during a dedicated Science Europe workshop (4 February) in Brussels. In this line, during the joint EC-ERA-LEARN workshop on 10–11 March, Science Europe called for research funding and performing organisations to be involved in the partnerships' overall governance. In June, Science Europe followed up with proposals sent to the relevant EC services. This initiative resulted in meetings with DG RTD's Director and the unit in charge of the European Partnerships.

RESEARCH POLICY AREAS

OPEN ACCESS

OPEN ACCESS (OA) IS THE PRACTICE OF GRANTING ACCESS TO SCHOLARLY OUTPUTS TO ANYONE

AT NO COST AND WITH NO OBSTACLES OR RESTRICTIONS OF ANY KIND.

It is part of the Open Science movement that has been developing for more than three decades. Science Europe strongly advocates the elimination of structural and geographical hurdles to facilitate the flow of knowledge for researchers. In this spirit, not only does OA benefit the research community itself, but it also enhances the efficient use of public funds for research, benefitting both the economy and society.

In 2020, Science Europe engaged in OA-related activities through its dedicated Working Group on Open Access to Research Publications and the work of cOAlition S in implementing Plan S.

Digital Transformation in Scholarly Communication

Building on work done in 2019, Science Europe published a forward-looking report on the [future of scholarly publishing](#) (8 April). This report outlined how the wake of new digital technologies is likely to act as a foundation for further transformational changes in scholarly communication. The report addressed a variety of OA-related issues such as the digital revolution, information dissemination, and research publishing practices.

Monitoring Open Access

To inform policies and actions contributing to OA transition, research organisations need reliable and up-to-date information on publications' statuses. That is why Science Europe spent considerable effort in 2020 developing tools to provide its MOs with a discussion forum and guidance on how to do so. Throughout the year, a task group of representatives from six Science Europe MOs met to discuss ways to monitor the status of research publications and progress toward OA. This culminated in a dedicated workshop with experts from within and outside of the Science Europe membership, on 20 October. A [publication](#) containing guidance on how to measure the OA status of scientific publications and improve the organisations' monitoring practices was released on 10 May 2021.

Science Europe spent considerable effort in 2020 developing tools to provide guidance on Open Access.

OA in EC's Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement

In 2020, the EC demonstrated its commitment to OA by planning to enshrine a strong OA policy in its Model Grant Agreement (MGA). In its involvement with Plan S and other OA-related activities, Science Europe provided the EC with expert insights to feed into its priorities for the MGA. More specifically, Science Europe did so on the first Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2021–2024 and through a letter sent to Commissioner Gabriel on 9 September. In both instances, Science Europe advocated a strong OA policy in Horizon Europe and requested immediate OA to all publications stemming from Horizon Europe projects.

Science Europe and cOAlition S

Started by eleven Science Europe MOs and launched in 2018, cOAlition S is now a global organisation. 2020 Marked a significant shift in how it operates, with Science Europe transferring the administrative and operational management to the European Science Foundation (ESF). Engagement with Plan S-related activities continued throughout 2020 via the Executive Steering Group, chaired by Science Europe's President, and the Experts Group. Science Europe hosted meetings in January to discuss the start of the Plan S roadmap implementation, and contributed to defining a [method](#) to monitor its effects on research and scholarly communication (including on early-career researchers). Moreover, it sponsored two studies: one defined the [data needed for authors](#) to identify Plan S-compliant publication venues (from which the [Journal Checker Tool](#) was developed). The other, of which the reach extended beyond cOAlition S, aimed to provide an in-depth understanding of the challenges that the [community-driven, non-commercial scholarly journal sector](#) (Diamond OA journals) faces in the field.'

RESEARCH POLICY AREAS

RESEARCH DATA

SCIENCE EUROPE AND ITS MOs PROMOTE THE SHARING, INTEROPERABILITY,

AND RE-USING OF QUALITY-ASSURED RESEARCH DATA AS GOOD SCIENTIFIC PRACTICE AND KEY TO OPEN SCIENCE.

Research Data Management (RDM) helps researchers plan how, when, and where to share what data. Many Research Funding Organisations and Research Performing Organisations have relevant policies in place. To avoid strong differences from one country or from one institution to another, MOs seek to align such policies and requirements across Europe. Science Europe also strives for research data to be sustainable, which includes their long-term storage and accessibility.

Research Data Management

On 29 January, Science Europe organised a [public event showcasing a best practice collection featuring experiences from several MOs](#) in successfully aligning data management policies. This work follows the uptake of the 2019 Science Europe [Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management](#).

The RDM Guide was widely implemented and used by many research stakeholders in Europe and beyond. Subsequently, experts from the Science Europe Working Group on Data Sharing and Supporting Infrastructures (WG DSSI) developed an evaluation rubric for Data Management Plans (DMPs). This tool, fully integrated into the RDM Guide, was presented during a [webinar held on 27 January 2021](#).

Throughout 2020, Science Europe pushed for RDM-related issues to feature on the EU Institutions' agenda. During the EC's consultation on the Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2021–2024, Science Europe [publicly responded](#) on 18 September asking the EC to reference the RDM Guide and the Framework for Discipline-specific RDM in the Horizon Europe MGA.

Sustainability of Research Data

In 2020, Science Europe worked to create maturity matrices to support its members and other organisations when they develop their organisational 'agenda for research data' to ensure sustainable research data. The ambition is for the matrices to be used by RFOs, RPOs, and research data infrastructures across Europe. Their release is scheduled for Spring 2021.

European Open Science Cloud

Science Europe took an active part in the discussions and policy developments leading towards the setup of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), as member of the EOSC Executive Board. Science Europe played a significant role as co-chair of the EOSC Sustainability Working Group from July 2019 to December 2020.

Science Europe strives for research data to be sustainable, which includes long-term storage and accessibility.

Science Europe's role in the EOSC was in line with its aim to promote Open Science and data sharing policies. To inform its members on strategic aspects and relevant EOSC developments, Science Europe ran a series of webinars throughout the year. A new non-profit organisation, the EOSC Association, was formally founded on 29 July and had its constitutional General Assembly on 17 December, during which Science Europe became an Observer member.

Data-related EU Legislation

In parallel to activities organised with and for its members, Science Europe monitored data-related developments on the EU legislation front. In February, the EC presented its European Strategy for Data. In [its reaction to the strategy](#), Science Europe stressed that policy, legislation, and guidance on data sharing across sectors should consider the practices and needs of the research sector in general, and of its MOs in particular. Science Europe invited the EC to build its reflection on existing good practices in the highly data-dependent research sector. Based on its Strategy for Data, the EC conducted a consultation on its plans to establish sectoral European Data Spaces. The Science Europe [response to this consultation](#) in July underlined the importance of recognising the already well-established data accessibility and interoperability standards and practices. Science Europe further provided input to other upcoming legislative dossiers by responding to consultations on the [Digital Services Act](#) and [Artificial Intelligence](#).

RESEARCH POLICY AREAS

GENDER
AND DIVERSITY

GENDER EQUALITY AND DIVERSITY ARE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF SCIENTIFIC QUALITY.

Science Europe works to promote a research ecosystem where all scholars can realise their potential, regardless of their gender, sexual orientation, religion, disabilities, ethnic origin, or social background. Ensuring the fairness of assessment processes is a top priority among Science Europe members. Recently, the importance of addressing systemic issues in the research ecosystem has led to a renewed focus on combatting all forms of discrimination and bias, addressing harassment and bullying, and promoting the integration of sex and gender in research content and priorities.

Science Europe provides concrete recommendations to promote gender equality.

As a member of the GRC's Gender Working Group (GWG), Science Europe worked to produce a report that analysed the data collection practices of research funders worldwide. The study, which will be launched during the Annual Meeting of the Global Research Council in May 2021, offers a comparative overview of trends and practices in different world regions. In addition, the report puts these data in perspective and provides reviews of the relevant scientific literature. On this basis, it provides concrete recommendations on improving data collections to promote gender equality. Science Europe has also spent parts of 2020 reflecting on the development of common guidelines to address bullying and harassment in academia and research organisations, which are expected for publication in 2021. This work is the continuation of a long-term endeavour that started in 2017 when Science Europe published its [Practical Guide to Improving Gender Equality in Research Organisations](#).

Over the course of the year, Science Europe also contributed to the Funders for Gender Equality Community of Practice (FORGEN), promoting fairness and equality in research assessment processes. Through FORGEN, Science Europe contributes to building a good knowledge base on proven and innovative initiatives that promote gender equality in research funding. During a dedicated workshop, organised by FORGEN in April 2020, a preliminary mapping of such initiatives was undertaken. As a follow-up activity, Science Europe is working with FORGEN to develop a toolbox for funders looking for examples of promising and proven initiatives.

Important links were drawn between this topic and Science Europe's activities related to research assessment processes (introduced on the following page). Recognising the important role that these processes can play in supporting equality and diversity in research, the topic of bias, discrimination, and unfair treatment was a central component of Science Europe's work on research assessment. Expertise and insight from its work on Gender and Diversity were fed into the policy recommendations published in 2020 on research assessment processes.

RESEARCH POLICY AREAS

RESEARCH
ASSESSMENT**ASSESSMENT IS KEY**

TO THE RESEARCH
ENTERPRISE.

It ensures quality of research and research processes and forms the basis for the recognition, rewards, and incentives systems, which must be carefully and continually adjusted to be fit for purpose. Science Europe brings together its members to showcase good practices and discuss ways to guarantee that research assessment processes are effective, efficient, fair, and transparent.

Science Europe started the year with an extensive [consultation on research assessment processes](#) of its MOs and the wider research community. Together with the survey, Science Europe distributed the report of its 2019 flagship [study on research assessment practices](#) carried out by Technopolis across its membership. On 28 April, Science Europe invited experts, researchers, and stakeholder representatives to further reflect on research assessment processes. This allowed Science Europe to incorporate advice from the science community into the development of relevant policy recommendations, providing important perspectives on the wide-ranging influence that assessment processes have on the research system as a whole.

Assessment ensures quality of research and research processes.

Building on the 2019 study and the subsequent expert dialogues, a [Position Statement and Recommendations on Research Assessment Processes](#) was published in July 2020. This statement represented an important consensus amongst Science Europe members on the current status of research assessment and provided a gold standard for assessment processes. These recommendations gave a framework for both RPOs and RFOs to adapt their assessment processes and join their efforts to tackle common challenges. The recommendations also allowed for reflection on where broader reforms to assessment processes were needed. The evidence base established across this activity will serve as an important reference point for future Science Europe actions on the topic.

Research Assessment was also at the heart of a GRC Conference on 23–27 November. Science Europe collaborated with the GRC on the [concept of responsible research assessment](#). Importantly, the 2019 Science Europe study was used as the basis for the [survey](#) that the GRC ran to inform the conference, taking many of the study's questions and posing them at a global level. Over a thousand international participants gathered to discuss initiatives such as the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), Science Europe's Position Statement, and the implementation of responsible research assessment in working practices of the research system around the world. In its contribution, Science Europe collated more than 20 of its [members' good practices](#) to illustrate novel assessment processes, the adaptation of assessment criteria to promote gender equality, and the transparent communication of procedures, as examples.

RESEARCH COLLABORATION

CROSS-BORDER AND INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION

KNOWLEDGE HAS ALWAYS TRANSCENDED BORDERS.

Yet, in an increasingly globalised research ecosystem, efficient collaboration has never been more vital. Researchers need to move across borders in diverse scientific and legal environments with as little administrative burden as possible. Science Europe MOs strive for European research to be the most competitive and excellent world-wide and to improve collaboration mechanisms. Since researchers routinely collaborate with one another outside of Europe, they encounter specific challenges dealing with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). It is therefore crucial for Science Europe MOs to receive support and advice on the issue.

Weave: the Multilateral Lead Agency (MLA) Agreement Initiative

On 18 December, Science Europe launched [Weave](#), a cross-European initiative to fund and support excellent international research projects. This is the first time that such a large number of agencies have come together to ease cross-border collaboration for researchers.

Researchers need to move across borders with as little administrative burden as possible.

Through Weave, the process of submitting and selecting collaborative research proposals involving researchers from up to three European countries or regions is now narrowed down to a single evaluation procedure. This initiative allows the researchers to have more freedom when deciding on the composition, focus, and content of their research projects. In practice, researchers from different countries planning a joint project choose a co-ordinating applicant, who submits the joint proposal to the respective Weave funding organisation in their country or region. This organisation then evaluates the proposal, with its decision being followed by the home institutes of the other applicants without further administrative procedure.

12 PARTICIPATING FUNDING ORGANISATIONS:

- Austrian Science Fund (FWF)
- Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)
- Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)
- Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)
- National Science Centre (NCN)
- Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)
- Fund for Scientific Research (FNRS)
- Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)
- German Research Foundation (DFG)
- Research Council of Norway (RCN)
- Slovenian Research Agency (ARRS)
- Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

Many Science Europe MOs encounter GDPR-related challenges when setting up cross-border research collaborations. These challenges refer to a lack of clarity in the GDPR and provisions that are not fit for public organisations. Science Europe engaged in a dialogue with EU authorities, including the office of the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS), the European Data Protection Board (EDPB), as well as the relevant services at the European Commission (DG Justice) to address these issues. Science Europe MOs provided examples where more guidance would be needed. On 2 September, the EDPB published new guidelines on processors and controllers in the GDPR and opened a consultation for stakeholder feedback to which Science Europe responded. In line with its commitment to align processes across its membership, Science Europe set up a task force to develop templates for all MOs to use in their agreements with international partners.

RESEARCH COLLABORATION

RESEARCH
INFRASTRUCTURES**EXCELLENT RESEARCH**

REQUIRES EXCELLENT
INFRASTRUCTURE.

As investment in Research Infrastructures (RIs) is so important for the conduct of research worldwide, it is crucial that a collaborative and internationally co-ordinated approach is taken to the funding, development, management, and operation of national RIs. Science Europe's contribution to this important topic is to facilitate fruitful dialogue between RI funders, decision makers, managers, and the diverse scientific communities that RIs support. Science Europe acts as an intermediary for RI stakeholders at national, European, and international levels, and promotes the important role(s) that RIs play as part of the research ecosystem.

Building on its 2019 engagement, 2020 saw further development in Science Europe's RI-related activities. It was also the year when the European public debate cast a particularly sharp focus on RIs because of the strategic role they play in the ERA. In parallel, Science Europe showcased its international relevance on the issue through activities and events organised jointly with the OECD Global Science Forum (GSF). In the wake of two surveys and two international workshops held in 2019, a joint policy paper

with the OECD-GSF under the title 'Optimising the Use and Operation of National Research Infrastructures' was published on 8 September. This paper was the culmination of an intense two-year partnership, during which Science Europe and OECD-GSF identified a number of key factors and guiding principles to help policy makers, decision makers, and infrastructure managers to optimise the use and operation of the infrastructures that they manage.

These principles were brought together in two 'Guiding Models' with policy recommendations to governments, funders, and RI management. The policy report targeted RI funders, decision makers, and managers, but also the wider research infrastructure community. The joint initiative developed specific recommendations and showcased good practice examples relating to optimising the use and operation of national RIs. Whilst maintaining a broad overview of national RI landscapes, the report also recognised and addressed important specificities related to the diversity of research fields supported and types of RIs needed to support world-class research.

Research Infrastructures play a strategic role in the ERA.

GUIDING MODELS FOR OPTIMISING THE OPERATION AND USE OF RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

The joint activity identified a wide range of management and operation policies and practices which influence the use of national research infrastructures. Reflecting this diversity, recommendations were developed in the form of two guiding models. These recommendations can be viewed on [Science Europe website](#).

RESEARCH COLLABORATION

GLOBAL RESEARCH
COUNCIL**THE GLOBAL RESEARCH COUNCIL (GRC) IS A VIRTUAL ORGANISATION CREATED IN 2011,**

COMPRISED OF THE HEADS OF SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING FUNDING AGENCIES FROM AROUND THE WORLD.

It is dedicated to promoting the sharing of data and best practices for high-quality collaboration among funding agencies worldwide. Science Europe has always co-operated closely with the GRC. This is embodied through the GRC Governing Board, on which the Science Europe President plus two MO Heads sit, as well as through Science Europe's participation in the GWG (see [page 19](#)).

Science Europe has always co-operated closely with the GRC.

As a consequence of the COVID-19 crisis, the GRC officially postponed its March 2020 Annual Meeting. Co-hosted by South Africa's National Research Foundation (NRF) and UK Research and Innovation, the meeting was re-scheduled for 24–27 May 2021, using a fully virtual platform.

From November 2020 on, each of the GRC Regions organised an event dedicated to COVID-19-related issues. Partnering with its member the German Research Foundation (DFG), Science Europe co-organised the COVID-19 event for the European Region on 14 January 2021. It addressed topics such as the management of COVID-19-related calls, remote peer review assessment, science–policy dialogue, and international collaboration.

In addition to the COVID-19 seminars, the GRC also organised a [conference on responsible research assessment](#) from 23–27 November. Over a thousand international participants gathered to discuss working practices of the research system globally.

FOR MORE INFORMATION ON THIS EVENT:

Please go to [page 20](#) (section Research Assessment).

2021 – WHAT IS NEXT FOR SCIENCE EUROPE

AS WE CONCLUDE OUR REFLECTIONS ON WHAT WAS A TRANSFORMATIONAL YEAR FOR RESEARCH, AND ONE WHICH HAS SHAPED THE FUTURE OF SCIENCE EUROPE, WE EAGERLY ANTICIPATE WHAT 2021 HAS TO OFFER.

Science Europe's strategy and multi-annual action plan for the coming years covers a broad suite of policy priorities all aiming to support its Member Organisations in their respective missions, whilst also gathering the collective knowledge of its members to contribute to EU policy development and to the advancement of European and global research and innovation systems.

As you will have read, in 2020 Science Europe explored the topic of research assessment processes and developed a set of policy recommendations that represent a current gold standard in the field. Many aspects of the current assessment system are bound by the ingrained and established methods by which research, researchers, and research institutes are recognised, incentivised, and rewarded for the work they conduct and disseminate.

As such, in 2021, Science Europe will initiate a deeper reflection on research culture via the recognition system of research.

Open Science will also remain a key priority. The association will strive to ensure continuous monitoring of and contribution to all Open Science-related policy debates and relevant EU-level policies, programmes, and legislation, as well as new initiatives from the research community. 2021 will also see the birth of a reflection on the way research culture is evolving, and how this transformation can drive the necessary adjustments to sustain excellent research systems in Europe.

I would like to thank the engagement of the Governing Board in shaping up the new Strategy Plan that will be launched in 2021 and will shape the association in the years to come. We will continue representing our Member Organisations, providing input to key research and innovation policy areas, while we strive to contribute to shaping a healthy research culture and promoting a better role and contribution of science to society. Finally, let me mention that Science Europe will celebrate its 10th anniversary in 2021, an excellent opportunity to gather and celebrate the successes over the years while looking to a bright future for science in Europe.

DR. LIDIA BORRELL-DAMIÁN

SECRETARY GENERAL OF SCIENCE EUROPE

“Science Europe strives to shape a healthy research culture and promote a better role and contribution of science to society.”

ANNEX

SCIENCE
EUROPE
Shaping the future of research

SCIENCE EUROPE GOVERNING BOARD

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Marc Schiltz (President)	Secretary General of the National Research Fund of Luxembourg (FNR)	Luxembourg
Ingrid Petersson (Vice-President representing RFOs)	Director General of the Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Rosa Menéndez (Vice-President representing RPOs)	President of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Zbigniew Blocki	Director of the National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Thierry Damerval	President/CEO of the French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Roland Fischer	Vice-President of the German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
József Györkös <i>until April 2020</i>	Director of the Slovenian Research Agency (ARRS)	Slovenia
Angelika Kalt	Director of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Darrin Morrissey <i>until June 2020</i>	Chief Executive of the Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
John-Arne Røttingen <i>until December 2020</i>	CEO of the Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Sven Stafström	Director General of the Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Melanie Welham	Executive Chair, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Antonio Zoccoli	President of the National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy

MEMBERS OF SCIENCE EUROPE'S COLLABORATION GROUPS

WORKING GROUP ON HORIZON 2020 AND HORIZON EUROPE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Reinhard Belocky	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Margot Beereboom	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Ann van Hauwaert	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Natacha Wittorski	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Anne Lindeløv	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Maria Alajõe <i>until August 2020</i>	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Ülle Napa <i>since August 2020</i>	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Hannele Lahtinen	Academy of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Nakita Vodjdani	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Rüdiger Hesse	Max Planck Society (MPG)	Germany
Elena Martins	Leibniz Association (WGL)	Germany
Martin Winger	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Peter Brown <i>until August 2020</i>	Irish Research Council (IRC)	Ireland
Deirdre Quinn <i>since August 2020</i>	Irish Research Council (IRC)	Ireland
Dolores Melgar <i>until November 2020</i>	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Maria Nash <i>since November 2020</i>	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Francesco Ferlaino	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Jūratė Deviženė	The Research Council of Lithuania (LMT)	Lithuania
Joyce Kuipers	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Tor Ivar Eikaas	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Tom-Espen Møller	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Sylwia Kostka	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Michał Pietras	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Tomasz Poprawka <i>until July 2020</i>	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ana Mafalda Dourado	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Berta Martínez	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Britta Fängström	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Maria Ulfvarson Dahlman <i>until May 2020</i>	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Maria Lindholm	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Rahel Byland (Co-chair)	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Inga Benner (Co-chair)	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

WORKING GROUP ON OPEN ACCESS TO RESEARCH PUBLICATIONS

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Katharina Rieck	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Jean-Claude Kita	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S-FNRS)	Belgium
Guy Thoonen	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Lovorka Barać Lauc	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Petr Chorošenin	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Marika Meltsas	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Jussi Varkemaa	Academy of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Zoé Ancion	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Georg Botz (Chair)	Max Planck Society (MPG)	Germany
Astrid Säger	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Olaf Siegert	Leibniz Association (WGL)	Germany
Marion Boland	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Patricia Clarke	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Laura Patrizii	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Ingmārs Kreišmanis	Latvian Science Council (LZP)	Latvia
Irmantas Pečiūra <i>until March 2020</i>	Research Council of Lithuania (LMT)	Lithuania
Hans de Jonge	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Jon Flæten	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Laura Bandura-Morgan	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Joana Novais	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Alina Irimia	The Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Agnès Ponsati Obiols	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Lisbeth Söderqvist	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Tommy Dahlen	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life & Welfare (FORTE)	Sweden
Tobias Philipp	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Paul Richards	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

WORKING GROUP DATA SHARING AND SUPPORTING INFRASTRUCTURES

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Katharina Rieck	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Jean-Claude Kita	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S-FNRS)	Belgium
Alexandra Vandervelde	Research Foundation Flanders	Belgium
Johanne Thorup-Dalgaard	Danish Council for Independent Research (DFF)	Denmark
Harri Hautala	Academy of Finland	Finland
Zoé Ancion <i>until September 2020</i>	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Gala Garcia Reategui <i>since September 2020</i>	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Michael Royeck	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Stefan Winkler-Nees (Chair)	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Reiner Mauer	Leibniz	Germany
Andreas Witt	Leibniz	Germany
Patricia Clarke	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Sharon Kappala <i>since July 2020</i>	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Aileen Sheehy <i>until March 2020</i>	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
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Artūras Kaklauskas	Research Council of Lithuania (LMT)	Lithuania
Ramunė Rudokienė	Research Council of Lithuania (LMT)	Lithuania
Tom Jakobs	National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxemburg
Hans de Jonge	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Maria Cruz	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Anne Elisabeth Solsnes	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Maria Pawłowska <i>until February 2020</i>	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Barbara Wajnchold <i>since July 2020</i>	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Laura Bandura-Morgan	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Filipa Pereira <i>since March 2020</i>	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Fernando Aguilar	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Joaquín Tintoré	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Sanja Halling	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Katrin Milzow	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Cornelia Sommer	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
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HIGH-LEVEL POLICY NETWORK ON CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Christoph Bärenreuter	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
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Olivier Boehme	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Isabelle Verbaeys	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Joël Groeneveld	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Jasminka Boljević	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Ana Ravnic Perfido	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Zuzana Naylor	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Johanna Hakala	Academy of Finland (AKA)	Finland

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
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Felix Kahle	Max Planck Society (MPG)	Germany
Michael Moessele	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Myriam Poll	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Mairéad O'Driscoll	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
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Rune Vistad	Research Council of Norway	Norway
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Justyna Woźniakowska	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Mojca Boc	Slovenian Research Agency (ARRS)	Slovenia
Berta Martínez	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Johan Lindell	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Katarina Nordqvist	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Jean-Luc Barras	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Isabel Bolliger	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
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TASK FORCE ON MULTILATERAL LEAD AGENCY

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Michael Royeck	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
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Toshiki Nagano	Japan Science and Technology Agency (JST)	Japan
Myeun Kwon	National Fusion Research Institute	Korea
Yong-Joo Kim	National Research Facilities and Equipment Center (NFEC)	Korea
Eun Ju Lee	Korea Basic Science Institute	Korea
Jeannette Ridder-Numan	Ministry of Education, Culture and Science	Netherlands
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Clifford Nxomani	National Research Infrastructure Platforms, NRF	South Africa
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Mirjam van Daalen	Paul Scherrer Institute PSI	Switzerland
Catherine Ewart (Chair)	UKRI- Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC)	United Kingdom
Samuel Howerton	National Science Foundation	United States
Robert Smith (Chris)	National Science Foundation	United States
Andrew Harrison	Association of European-level Research Infrastructure Facilities	ERF AISBL
Florian Gliksohn	Association of European-level Research Infrastructure Facilities	ERF AISBL
Jean-Luc Barras	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Isabel Bolliger	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Michael Royeck	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Oonagh Ward	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
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Carthage Smith	GSF secretariat	OECD
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TASK FORCE ON GDPR IN INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH COLLABORATIONS

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Ulrike Varga	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Tinne Jacobs	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Veroniek Robinne	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Petr Chorošenin	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Kati Uusmaa	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Joanna Faruga <i>until July 2020</i>	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Sophie Grelat <i>since July 2020</i>	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Nakita Vodjdani	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Chiara Loda	Irish Research Council (IRC)	Ireland
Marius Dijokas	Research Council of Lithuania (LMT)	Lithuania
Asaël Rouby	National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxemburg
Anja Wiesbrock	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Beata Habuda	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Alex Bailey	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Paul Wiley	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

FINANCE COMMITTEE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Hans Willems	Research Foundation Flandres (FWO)	Belgium
Jurij von Kreisler	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Marc Rock	National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxemburg
Debbie Kay	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

GB TASK FORCE ON VISION AND STRATEGY

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Roland Fischer	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
John-Arne Røttingen	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Marc Schiltz	National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxemburg
Sven Stafström	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Angelika Kalt	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Melanie Welham	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

GB TASK FORCE ON THE ARTICLES OF ASSOCIATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Thierry Damerval	National Agency for Research (ANR)	France
Marc Schiltz	National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxemburg

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NAME	TITLE
Lidia Borrell-Damián	Secretary General
Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch	Head of Research Affairs
Maud Evrard	Head of Policy Affairs
Fekria Allachi	Head of Finance and Human Resources
Marie Timmermann	Senior Policy Officer
Mathilde Reumaux	Senior Policy Officer
James Morris	Senior Policy Officer
Adrien Braem	Policy Officer
Lorna Stokes	Communications Manager
Hayet Zeghiche	Communications Manager (Parental Leave Cover)
Iwan Groeneveld	Events and Publications Officer
Artemis Rodopoulou	Officer Manager
Lauren O'Connor	Personal and Administrative Assistant

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

PUBLICATION DATE	TITLE
29 January	Implementing Research Data Management Policies Across Europe: Experiences from Science Europe Member Organisations
4 February	Science Europe Study on Research Assessment Practices
8 April	Workshop Report on Digital Transformation in Scholarly Communication
2 June	Response to the European Commission Consultation on the European Strategy for Data
15 June	Europe to Keep Leading COVID-19 Pandemic and Crisis Recovery
18 June	Strengthening European Research: Funding Boost Needed to Guarantee Sustainability
9 July	Position Statement and Recommendations on Research Assessment Processes
22 July	Reaction to the European Council's Proposal for the European Budget
31 July	Response to the European Commission Roadmap on European Data Spaces

PUBLICATION DATE

TITLE

28 August	SE-OECD Policy Paper on Optimising the Operation and Use of National Research Infrastructures
8 September	Response to the European Commission's Inception Impact Assessment on the Digital Services Act
10 September	Response to the European Commission's Inception Impact Assessment on Artificial Intelligence
18 September	Response to the European Commission Consultation on the Horizon Europe First Strategic Plan 2021-2024
16 October	Response to the EDPB Consultation on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR
17 December	Report of the 2020 High Level Workshop on ERA: The ERA Contribution to the post-COVID-19 Recovery and Transition to a Resilient Society

LIST OF EVENTS**DATE**

TITLE

27-28 January	Workshop on the GDPR in International Collaborations
4 February	European Partnerships
24 March	Consultation Event on Research Assessment Processes
20 October	Workshop on Monitoring Open Access to Scholarly Publications
18 November	High Level Workshop on ERA 2020
14 December	1st SE-NSFC Scientists' Networking Workshop on COVID-19

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Science Europe is the association representing major public organisations that fund or perform excellent, ground-breaking research in Europe.

We bring together the expertise of some of the largest and best-known research organisations in the world to jointly push the frontiers of how scientific research is produced and delivers benefits to society.

We advocate science and the scientific community to help build the European Research Area and shape the global scientific agenda.

More information on our mission and activities is provided at www.scienceeurope.org

